

A Hand Mechanical Tracker with Tactile Rendering for Fine Telemanipulation

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Abstract—In this paper, we present a mechanical hand-tracking system with tactile feedback designed for fine manipulation in teleoperation scenarios. Alternative tracking methods based on artificial vision and data gloves have become an asset for virtual reality interaction. Yet, occlusions, lack of precision, and the absence of effective haptic feedback beyond vibrotactile still appear as a limit for teleoperation applications. We propose a methodology to design a linkage mechanism for hand pose tracking purposes, preserving complete finger mobility. Tracking accuracy was evaluated and a teleoperation experiment was involved on ten participants with a dexterous robotic arm and hand.

I. INTRODUCTION

The quality of manipulation becomes essential when telemanipulation tasks are performed in critical scenarios [1]. In such a context, precise hand-tracking and high quality haptic information are crucial factors in terms of the stability of the grasp, inside-hand, and fine manipulation.

Nowadays optical tracking technology represents an asset in a variety of applications due to the immediateness of use and together with the widespread of virtual reality systems.

Yet optical fingers tracking has to deal with silhouette scales, the unavoidable occlusions which are due to the interposition of obstacles between the cameras and the designated surfaces, but also to fingers overlapping that might occur in certain manipulation pose [2]. Besides purely optical devices exclude the sense of touch.

On another side, data gloves are a commonly used solution in virtual reality interactions and video-gaming. These systems offer the facility of integrating a large variety of sensors with adequate transparency and wearability. Nonetheless, a lack of precision may occur due to unavoidable slips which happen between the bending sensors and the fingers and also between the IMU and the hand. As a consequence, gloves can result less suitable than vision-based devices for remote manipulation tasks [3].

So far two different approaches to haptic feedback have been mainly investigated: on one side, kinaesthetic force feedback provided by active hand exoskeleton devices [4], on the other side, tactile feedback is rendered by fingertip devices [5]. While the latter do not apply an absolute force opposing finger closure, but render only cutaneous perception at the fingerpad, they have the advantage of significantly smaller design and

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Fig. 1. The proposed mechanical hand-tracking system endorsing serial kinematic chains for precise fingers pose estimation and voice-coils on the fingertips for tactile feedback.

enhanced wearability. Moreover, tactile feedback can provide highly informative haptic stimuli as well, especially in fine manipulation tasks, where both dynamic transients and fine modulation of the grasping force play a significant role [6].

In this paper, we introduce a Mechanical Hand-Tracking (MHT) system, Fig. 1, combining accurate finger tracking and high mobility with tactile stimulation. In particular, the use of a serial kinematic chain mechanism for fingers tracking is investigated under lightweight and full fingers mobility requirements. The device is endorsed with potentiometric sensors to capture the finger pose while voice-coils actuators, located at the fingertip, provide tactile feedback.

II. DESIGN

In this work, the classical kinematic hand model proposed in [7] and for this, we adopted some simplifications on fingers motion. For designing a MHT, a preliminary choice concerns the location of the anchor point between the finger and the MHT chain. In this regard, several aspects have been considered, such as: i) ergonomics; ii) size; iii) finger mobility; iv) the encumbrance of the haptic interface on the distal phalanx. Consequently, the anchor point is located on the proximal phalanx for the long fingers, while it occurs on the distal phalanx for the thumb.

The main objective of the kinematic design is to find the strictly necessary number of Parallel Kinematic Chains (PKC) joints/DoFs that ensures full finger mobility. Indeed, the introduction of additional DoFs might result in: i) increased

complexity and weight; ii) further control effort in the case of telemanipulation; iii) redundancy, i.e. non-uniqueness of a single MHT configuration for a given configuration of the finger. To this purpose, the Screw Theory (ST) methodology is adopted. At last, a links length optimization is carried out for adaptation to every fingers size.

III. EXPERIMENTAL TESTS AND VALIDATION

Firstly, a characterization was performed with the aim to evaluate the measurement accuracy of the MHT. To this end, the hand-tracking measurement is compared with a ground-truth reference, represented by the measurement of an optical tracking system (Optitrack V120 Trio).

Then, we conducted an experimental study to evaluate the effectiveness of the MHT device performing hand-tracking with simultaneous tactile feedback for telemanipulation purposes.

The task was proposed to participants with two different target objectives:

- TEST A: fast manipulation - the user was asked to succeed in the task as fast as possible in a row of 10 trials;
- TEST B: precise manipulation - the user was asked to succeed in the task with the highest rate of success in a row of 5 trials, with no timing constraint, and with the explicit indication to perform a grasp "as soft as possible" without compromising the completion of the task.

Both experimental conditions were performed with (w HF) and without (w/o HF) haptic feedback. The sequence of the four possible experimental conditions was randomized. Finally, a NASA Task Load Index questionnaire was proposed to subjects at the end of the experiment. Its results did not evidenced stress or discomfort of the participants.

IV. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Validation of the fingertip tracking accuracy for the long finger mechanism reported a mean error of 3 mm: this shows a noticeably better performance than data gloves and vision-based systems compared in [3]. Regarding the evaluation of the overall system design and implementation, experiments validated the usability and effectiveness of the system in an applied teleoperation setup. During the comparative teleoperation tests the median success rate was equal to 93.75% for the w and 94.17% for the w/o HF with no significant difference. The relatively low occurrence of errors (object dropped) indicates that the system was usable by different subjects with a relatively short training time (15 minutes); it is also an indication of the overall reliability of the tracking.

Figure 2 reports the box plots of the average variability and the average grasping pressure during the fast and precise task in the two conditions. On one side, the presence of tactile feedback did not produce a significant direct reduction of the applied forces, both in the A and B tasks. On the other side, the analysis of pressure variability over repetitions (see top plot) suggests that haptic feedback was indeed informative of

Fig. 2. Mean and mean standard grasping pressure across the telemanipulation tasks for different target objectives and tactile stimula (HF) - with (w) or without (w/o).

grasping force modulation, guiding subjects to a modulation strategy more consistent between subsequent repetitions.

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